

A ROUTE TO SHAPE CORRECT/SHAPE STABLE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The underlying mechanisms of manufacturing distortion in composite materials have been suggested to be anisotropy, material property gradients, and part-tool interactions. These mechanisms have been further sub-divided into those that result in shape change with changing temperature (thermoelastic) and those that are one-time only effects (non-thermoelastic), generally related to isothermal cure shrinkage. The anisotropy and material property gradient mechanisms are predicted to be composed of both thermoelastic and non-thermoelastic contributions; however, distortion due to part-tool interaction seems to be only non-thermoelastic in nature. Since one very key goal of research into manufacturing induced distortion is to understand how to make undistorted parts, it is worth considering the ramifications of the thermoelastic and non-thermoelastic contributions.

In previous efforts to correct the distorted shape, it has been possible to generate laminates of correct shape by using non-net shape tooling and by varying the local stacking sequence. Unfortunately each of these approaches results in a component, which still changes shape with temperature, due to the thermoelastic contributions. Further research has even suggested ways to “balance” the thermoelastic response, creating a shape stable component; however, the resulting component will not match the tool shape due to effects of the non-thermoelastic component. Thus, an investigation into the application of a non-thermoelastic-only mechanism to separately balance the shape and thermal stability is undertaken.

Autoclave-cured angle brackets were produced with variations in the local stacking sequence in an attempt to balance the thermoelastic contributions, while two different mold release materials were applied to investigate the role of part-tool interaction. It was determined that the shape change with temperature could be readily adjusted and that the non-thermoelastic , shape change contribution could be separately affected. This indicates that, with further optimization, shape stable-shape correct angle brackets can be fabricated through the application of part-tool interactions.

Key Terms: Manufacturing distortion, warpage, anisotropy, part-tool interactions

INTRODUCTION

Composite parts, even flat plates, tend to warp during processing. Many composite parts are also shape unstable throughout their service life. In fact, the production of precision composite panels of complex geometry is often an iterative process that requires preliminary tooling to be developed and then modified, based on the distorted shape of test panels. This results in high costs and has been an impediment to the use of composite components. Much of the early work on the subject of manufacturing distortion dealt with uneven bleeding and part-tool sticking;[1] however, no analytical relationships were developed. Various underlying mechanisms of manufacturing induced distortion in composite materials

have been suggested. These mechanisms include anisotropy, material property gradients, and part-tool interactions, and they have been further sub-divided into those that result in shape change with changing temperature (thermoelastic) and those that are one-time only effects (non-thermoelastic) generally related to isothermal cure shrinkage.

While the coupling between out-of-plane deflection and in-plane stress in asymmetric laminates is widely recognized, it is conversely reasoned that symmetric laminates show shape stability. This belief is based on flat plate experience, but unfortunately, it is often extended to cases of more complex geometries without further consideration. However, the in-plane and out-of-plane composite properties can be vastly different, and will cause distortion in symmetric laminates that are not flat. To demonstrate this effect, many researchers have investigated the distortion of composite angle brackets. This problem is apparent even in certain geometrically symmetric, closed cross-sections. Composite components such as rectangular tubes or satellite waveguides may show distortions such as "dog-boning", as the sides of the rectangle tend to bow inward [2]. When the closed geometry is stiff enough to resist significant distortion, this "anisotropy mechanism" results in a build up of internal residual stresses rather than macroscopic shape distortion.

Many factors must be considered in solving the problem of manufacturing distortion. Anisotropic thermal contraction and isothermal cure shrinkage of the polymer matrix are two commonly cited factors affecting warpage. Other contributing factors that have been briefly studied are tooling material properties [3], fiber misalignment [4,5], and fiber volume fraction gradients [5,6]. Several models exist that take into account these factors [7,8,9,10,11,12,13], attempting to predict the process-induced stresses and, thus, warpage. In thick laminates severe through-thickness property gradients, such as variations in degree-of-cure, are predicted to develop, resulting in a stress imbalance and warpage. In thinner, composite laminates volume fraction gradients introduced during resin bleeding, can lead to measurable distortion even in flat plates. The resulting laminates are effectively unsymmetric and respond to changes in temperature and to cure shrinkage.

Within each mechanism, there is a need for further subdivision to separate effects that will produce life long shape instability from those producing distortion only during manufacture [14]. To satisfy this need to resolve the factors affecting manufacturing distortion from those that are driven by changes in the operating environment these contributions have been categorized into two principal components:

- (1) thermoelastic (reversible) contributions, and
- (2) non-thermoelastic (irreversible) cure and manufacturing contributions.

TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

The majority of the research to-date related to manufacturing distortion has focused on the relationship between the anisotropic nature of a laminate and part shape complexity, or on variations of the material properties through the laminate thickness. Each of these basic mechanisms has both thermoelastic and non-thermoelastic contributions. Other researchers have undertaken to demonstrate that interactions between the composite part and the fabrication tooling result in manufacturing induced distortion. The results of these works indicate that this part-tool mechanism, or the introduction of a cure stress gradient, has only a non-thermoelastic contribution. While the focus of much manufacturing induced distortion research has been on the underlying mechanisms, it is not clear that the importance of demonstrating a mechanism that is only non-thermoelastic has been discussed.

Since one very key goal of research into manufacturing induced distortion is to understand how to make undistorted parts, it is worth considering the ramifications of the thermoelastic and non-

thermoelastic contributions. Experience has shown that room temperature part shape can be “corrected” by utilizing tooling which is non-net shape. However, the resulting tool can be very complicated and cannot be directly used, after processing, as a quality check. Further, the resulting component shape is still dependent on temperature. Tests have also shown that shape correct “angle brackets” can be produced on net shape tooling through the use of localized stacking sequence asymmetry [15,16]. Unfortunately, these shape correct components are generally more highly unstable with temperature than those laminates produced on non-net shape tools. Ultimately, both solutions suffer from the fact that the shape is only correct for one specific temperature.

Shape stable “angle brackets” have also been demonstrated, using asymmetric lamination to balance the thermoelastic process induced distortions [15,16]. However, this solution still results in a distorted shape due to non-thermoelastic contributions, and a non-net shape tool is required if a shape correct/shape stable component is to be developed, as demonstrated schematically in Figure 1. It follows that if every mechanism of process-induced distortion includes both a thermoelastic contribution and a non-thermoelastic contribution, a solution for a shape stable/shape correct component produced on net shape tooling will not be possible. Thus, the acceptance of part-tool interaction as a mechanism, of process induced distortion, that is only non-thermoelastic in nature, means that, at least for simple shapes, a solution should exist that allows the development of a shape correct/shape stable component on net shape tooling.

The goals of this research are to show the lack of significant thermoelastic contribution for distortion introduced by part-tool interaction and to demonstrate that changing interaction parameters between the part and tool during processing can vary the relative degree of distortion. This is predicted to lead to the ability to design a product, and process, that results in a shape stable/shape correct part on net-shape tooling.

Figure 1 - Schematic approach to a Shape Stable/Shape Correct component.

Preliminary Design of a Shape Stable-Shape Correct Angle Bracket

Proposed methods of correcting distorted shapes have included extra stiffeners and a variation of materials used through the thickness to yield a radial gradient in expansion properties [2]. A radial variation in expansion is obtained through the use of hybrid laminates that can counter the effects of either moisture or temperature. However, the differences in the thermal and moisture expansion coefficients are such that this method cannot be used to simultaneously solve both instabilities. The method, initially proposed by this researcher, makes use of a mid-plane curvature due to in-plane/out-of-plane coupling in asymmetric laminated plates, which occurs in response to hygrothermal variations [15,17]. By balancing the change in curvature related to the thermoelastic contribution of the

anisotropy mechanism of distortion with an equal and opposite curvature predicted for a flat asymmetric laminate, a solution is available for variations in both moisture and temperature simultaneously. In previous work, an equivalent flat plate curvature [15,16,17] was defined and a closed form interactive approach, based on classical laminated plate theory was applied to determine the necessary asymmetric stacking sequence and fraction of the corner arc length.

Experimental results, using the laser reflection technique [14], have substantiated these relationships and show that prediction of optimized, thermally shape stable laminates is possible when only the anisotropy mechanism is considered. However, a simultaneous solution to both the non-thermoelastic and the thermoelastic distortion has not been determined unless non-net shape tooling is employed. Difficulties involved in correctly predicting the through-thickness laminate properties present the largest single source of error between the measured thermoelastic shape change and that predicted by the analysis [18,19]. Today, many computer numerical approaches are applied that can determine the degree of stacking sequence asymmetry necessary to offset the thermoelastic distortion contributions.

In the present work the equivalent flat plate approach was used to estimate a locally asymmetric stacking sequence, for 8-ply $(0/90)_2s$ angle brackets, that would offset the thermoelastic component of distortion. In addition to the locally asymmetric region, variations in part-tool interaction were then implemented to assess the ability to offset the non-thermoelastic component, separately.

EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENT OF DISTORTION

To experimentally investigate the ability to combine mechanisms of distortion in such a way as to offset both the thermoelastic and the non-thermoelastic contributions measurements of distortion were performed on both nominally flat laminate specimens and on angle bracket specimens. The measurements of distortion in nominally flat specimens are included to demonstrate that the part-tool interaction has only a non-thermoelastic contribution, and that the degree of non-thermoelastic distortion due to part-tool interaction can be adjusted by changing the material at the part-tool interface. In addition, for the specific composite material of this study, the flat panel testing was also included to determine the thermoelastic contribution that could be related to material properties gradients.

Laminated composite angle brackets, of nominally 90° included angle, are used as a demonstration of a more complex geometry, which is expected to show distortion related to all of the mechanisms described in the previous sections. The angle bracket-style specimen has been used extensively, by researchers, [14,20] to evaluate the components of processing induced distortion in laminated composites. In the present research, angle brackets were evaluated with varying degrees of localized stacking sequence asymmetry and with differing part-tool interaction contributions, to test the ability to adjust processing conditions and laminate design to generate a shape stable-shape correct product on net-shape tooling.

Flat Panel Contour Measurement Apparatus

To perform measurements of composite laminate distortion over a range of temperatures a custom panel contour mapping apparatus has been developed and is shown in Figure 2(a). The apparatus utilizes an oven, containing the specimens, that moves in the X-Y plane under an insulated glass plate allowing the operator to observe and control the motion. A Linear Voltage Displacement Transducer (LVDT) generating a voltage proportional to the out-of-plane displacement is in contact with the specimen and the probe is counterbalanced to minimize the contact force. All data is automatically collected using computerized data acquisition. The oven size can accommodate 30.5 cm x 30.5 cm square specimens with out-of-plane distortions up to 7.6 cm. A temperature controller regulates power to a heating element

and maintains the specimen at desired temperatures. A small electric fan is installed to ensure a uniform thermal environment.

This apparatus allows the contour of a panel to be measured at temperatures ranging from room temperature to 200°C. The data to generate the surface map is obtained isothermally, in multiple passes over the specimen surface, creating a set of Z-data corresponding to positions on an X-Y grid over the specimen surface. Data is post processed and contour maps representing the data, and thus the shape at each temperature, can be plotted. This information can be further manipulated to determine the thermoelastic and non-thermoelastic contributions to distortion.

Figure 2 – Experimental apparatus used for measurement of distortion
(a) flat panel contour mapping, (b) angle bracket measurement schematic, (c) angle bracket in oven

Angle Bracket Distortion Measurement Apparatus

A laser rotation technique is used to measure the included angle as a function of temperature [14]. The technique requires mounting the angle bracket specimen by one arm in a heated chamber with a small mirror attached to the tool surface of each arm as shown schematically in Figure 2(b). The laser is aimed through the chamber window at the mirror on one arm and the resulting reflected beam is aligned with the reference mark on the projection screen as seen in Figure 2(c). The specimen is then rotated until the reflection from the mirror on the second arm aligns with the reference mark. An encoder electronically measures the shaft rotation and the included angle is determined. This measurement is repeated in the reverse direction to bring the specimen back into its original position and allow a second check of each measured included angle. Using this approach, measurement of specimens with included angles ranging from 60° to 145° can be accomplished. One pulse of the encoder corresponds to an included angle increment of less than 0.02° and the reproducibility of measurement is on the order of ± 1 pulse. All room temperature shapes are confirmed using direct measurement with a high precision adjustable protractor. Tool angles were measured with the protractor, as well, and the measured value is used in the follow-up evaluation.

Included angle measurements of the angle bracket specimens were made at room temperature (24°C) and at elevated temperatures. Each specimen was measured with the rotation technique in roughly 14°C temperature increments to 122°C. Once the maximum temperature was reached, included angle measurements were repeated, as the chamber was cooled to room temperature, to observe the repeatability of the thermoelastic response. The rotation technique simplifies the measurement of thermoelastic response, without sacrificing precision or accuracy, and allows the included angle to be measured directly at the desired temperature.

Experimental Approach and Materials Used

T650/950 carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg specimens were autoclave cured with a cure pressure of 80 ± 5 psi, a cure temperature of $125\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$, a $3.5\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ heating rate and a cooling rate of about $0.7^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. Flat panel testing used 4-layer $[0/90]_S$ laminates, which were trimmed to specimens approximately 25mm wide and 250mm long.

Nominally flat specimens were produced with varying amounts of bleeder material to investigate the effect of changing material property gradients, by changing the degree of consolidation and correspondingly, any volume fraction gradients. Two different part-tool “interfaces” were generated through the use of a film mold release and a spray-on PTFE mold release. These different interfaces were used to change the level of stress, due to differential thermal expansion, transferred from the tool to the part.

Angle bracket specimens were composed of 8 plies and were cured on concave aluminum tooling with a tooling corner radius of 12.7mm. All angle bracket specimens were prepared with an amount of bleeder equivalent to the greatest amount used in the flat panel evaluations. Three different crossply laminate stacking sequences were manufactured, each based on $(0/90)_{2S}$. The baseline version used the symmetric $(0/90)_{2S}$ sequence throughout the angle bracket, while the other specimens incorporated a [Tool/(0/90/90/90/90/0/0/0)/Vacuum Bag] stacking sequence in the radiused corner region. The first of these sets of locally asymmetric angle brackets included the modified stacking sequence throughout the complete curved region, while the second set of specimens was asymmetric over only half of the corner arc length. The remaining regions of these locally asymmetric specimens retained the $(0/90)_{2S}$ lamination.

Two different part-tool “interfaces” were generated to investigate the effectiveness of part-tool interaction as a way of compensating for manufacturing distortion. On concave tooling, increased part-tool interaction will tend to offset the non-thermoelastic contribution from the anisotropy mechanism, which is related to the greater through-thickness than in-plane cure shrinkage. The variation in part-tool interaction was achieved, as in the flat panel testing, through the use of a film mold release and a spray-on PTFE mold release.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flat Panel Distortion Results

Figure 3 displays measured total curvatures and thermoelastic components of distortion for specimens tested with different numbers of bleeder plies and release methods. The results are grouped based on release method. Figure 4 shows micrographs of two specimens, cut at a 45° angle to the fibers so that both the 0 and 90 degree directions are clearly visible. Both laminates of Figure 4 were produced in the same autoclave batch. The micrograph on the left shows the laminate resulting from the use of 2 bleeder plies, while the laminate on the right had no resin bled. The measured thermoelastic contribution is essentially insignificant, but the trends suggest a slight variation in material property gradient with increasing amounts of bleeder. Conversely, the total measured distortion is definitely significant and thus, Figure 3 can be considered to show the trend in the non-thermoelastic contribution.

Two important results are determined, i) specimens produced using the film release have lower distortion than those produced using spray release, and ii) the changing degree of consolidation only seems to effect the non-thermoelastic curvature measured for the spray release part-tool interface. These results are interpreted to indicate that the film release does effectively separate the part from the tool, thus, suppressing the residual stress gradients. Further, the results indicate that the part-tool induced

residual stress gradients can be tailored through changes in consolidation and resulting changes in stress transfer from the tool to the part during cure. Since the Stress Gradient Mechanism is considered to be only non-thermoelastic in nature, these results are important to the ability to generate a design methodology for overcoming manufacturing distortion. Because the effect seems to be able to be varied through both changing consolidation, and mold release choices, options become apparent for tailoring this non-thermoelastic contribution and ultimately for developing shape correct/shape stable composites. Thus, the variations in part-tool interaction are expected to show a change in the non-thermoelastic component of distortion in the locally asymmetric angle brackets.

Figure 3 – Distortion Related to Process Variables

Figure 4 - Consolidation Variation

Angle Bracket Distortion Results

Angle bracket distortion results presented in Figure 5 are averages of pairs of specimens and several measurements. It is noted that the downward slope of the fully symmetric laminates is as expected, indicating that the thermoelastic distortion is greater, further from the process temperature. For the angle brackets prepared with asymmetric stacking sequences throughout the corner radius, the effect overcompensates for the thermoelastic contribution, resulting in angle brackets which actually open with decreasing temperature. The specimens with the asymmetric stacking sequence only over one half the corner radius arc length show a much reduced thermoelastic response, varying less than 0.1° over the 100°C range of temperature. These results indicate that for an angle bracket with the (0/90/90/90/90/0/0/0) local stacking sequence, slightly more than half the corner radius arc length would generate a zero slope and thus, a shape stable component.

Comparing the results for the specimen groups with the film release to the spray release, it is noted that in each case, the slopes are essentially unaffected, but the total distortion is greater with the film. This is the opposite of the trend measured in the flat laminates of the previous section, but is consistent with the goal of reduced angle bracket distortion. Since the flat plate curvature was increasingly convex-up with increasing stress transfer to the part, when the same effects are implemented in the concave-tooled angle bracket, enhanced part-tool driven distortion will tend to open up the included angle. This indicates that the spray release was transferring more stress to the laminate, resulting in more part-tool related compensation for the non-thermoelastic contributions of the other mechanisms. For the angle bracket, on concave tooling, this effect leads to a reduction in the total non-thermoelastic distortion. Further, the extent of the reduction in non-thermoelastic distortion seems dependent on the details of the stacking sequence and the amount of asymmetric material in contact with the tool. This is indicated by the larger difference between the lines for film and spray for the “full radius” specimens versus the difference noted in the “half radius” specimens. Thus, the results suggest that alternative localized asymmetric stacking sequences may offer differing degrees of part-tool interaction, indicating that the potential exists for design solutions that can overcome the total amount of non-thermoelastic distortion.

Figure 5 – Results of Spring-In versus Temperature

Overall, the laminate local asymmetric stacking sequence used in this experiment, over a fraction of the corner arc length intermediate to the two tested, and the spray release would seem to result in a shape stable angle bracket (zero slope) which still shows a total distortion of approximately 0.35° , all related to non-thermoelastic effects. This represents a room temperature reduction in the total distortion to about one third the value of distortion for the standard, symmetric laminates. The results also indicate a reduction of about 60% in the non-thermoelastic contribution due to the spray mold release, on the locally asymmetric laminate versus the symmetric laminate and film release.

To retain the thermoelastic stability, yet remove the remaining non-thermoelastic distortion a number of approaches may be effective. It is possible that even more stress transfer between the part and tool may be able to be generated, which would further reduce the non-thermoelastic distortion. It is also possible that changing the asymmetric stacking sequence, of the local corner region, may enable a greater transfer of part-tool related stresses, increasing the stress gradient and the non-thermoelastic corrective action. Unfortunately, this approach is only effective on concave tooling, since on convex tooling the non-thermoelastic contribution from the part-tool interaction would add to the non-thermoelastic distortion related to the anisotropy mechanism.

FUTURE WORK

In extending the present research, it seems that more effort needs to be focused on the effects of alternative asymmetric stacking sequences. Alternative stacking sequences can be designed to have a greater, or lesser, distortion than the asymmetric laminate used in the present work. This variation in the “strength” of the asymmetry would lead to varying required fractions of the corner region to contain the locally modified stacking sequence. Both the variation in the local stacking sequence and the variation of the arc length over which it acts may have an effect on how the part-tool stresses are transferred, further

allowing increased potential for optimization, and ultimately enabling the generation of shape stable/shape correct angle brackets.

Recent articles would suggest that the part-tool interaction is a small factor as the laminate thickness increases, and that the distortion due to anisotropy becomes the controlling factor in part distortion. Yet, industry continues to expend significant capital in the production of matched CTE tooling. If the part-tool interaction is a minor effect, this expenditure would not seem justified, and for tooling for simple shapes, such as the angle brackets used in much of the part distortion research, this is most likely true. However, the parts and the associated tooling used by industry are generally much more complex, and the tooling very often mechanically constrains the component. This means that without matched CTE's, the part can see a substantial amount of strain and the resulting stresses can lead to large distortions. Thus, to further investigate the effects of mechanical interlocking of the tool and part, in addition to the other mechanisms, future work will utilize paired angle bracket tooling, or channel tooling, of both convex and concave geometry.

CONCLUSIONS

Measurements of the flat symmetric panel distortion due to manufacture indicate that varying degrees of consolidation can have a large effect on the magnitude of the distortion. It is also noted that the amount of distortion due to part-tool interactions can be adjusted through changes in the "mold release", which effectively changes the amount of stress transferred from the tool to the part due to differences in thermal expansion. The experimental results also indicate that the distortion due to part-tool interaction is only non-thermoelastic in nature.

For the angle bracket specimens, the measured distortions indicate that the use of local regions of asymmetry can definitely modify the thermoelastic behavior of the angle bracket and can therefore be used to develop a shape stable product. In addition, it is indicated that, for angle brackets produced on concave tooling, the part-tool induced stress gradients can be used to separately offset the non-thermoelastic effects related to the anisotropy mechanism and to cure shrinkage, leading to decreased non-thermoelastic distortion. Thus, the results indicate that, with further optimization, and through separation of the thermoelastic and non-thermoelastic contribution, laminate and process designs can be determined that will result in a shape stable–shape correct angle bracket, when molded on net-shape concave tooling.

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